

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D4.1 Report on the Overall Plant Layout

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SUMMARY	<p>This document is the deliverable D4.1 of the project POLYPHEM. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 4 (System Integration and Overall Plant Design).</p> <p>In this task the overall plant design for the plant prototype of the POLYPHEM solar thermal combined cycle plant has been carried out. The sub-systems of the prototype under development in other work packages - solar receiver (WP1), solar-driven micro gas-turbine (WP2) and thermal energy storage (WP3) - have been aligned amongst each other and integrated into the existing THEMIS solar tower facility in order to form the complete solar-to-electric conversion chain of the prototype plant.</p> <p>Furthermore, based on the final design of the sub-components and on the planned operating strategies, the interconnections between the main components and the auxiliary equipment have been defined.</p>	
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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Table of Content

1. INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION	10
1.2 OBJECTIVES AND TASKS	10
2. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF THE PROTOTYPE SITE.....	11
2.1 WEATHER DATA	13
3. SUB COMPONENTS	16
3.1 HELIOSTAT FIELD	16
3.2 TOP CYCLE: AIR BRAYTON CYCLE	18
3.2.1 Solar Receiver.....	18
3.2.2 Solar receiver modules material selection and manufacturing process.....	21
3.2.3 Micro gas turbine	22
3.2.4 Combustion Chamber.....	25
3.2.5 Generator.....	26
3.2.6 Frequency Converter	26
3.3 RECOVERY HEAT EXCHANGER: CONNECTING TOP AND BOTTOM CYCLE	27
3.4 BOTTOM CYCLE: THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE AND ORC-PROCESS.....	29
3.4.1 Heat Transfer Fluid.....	29
3.4.2 Thermal Energy Storage.....	30
3.4.3 Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC).....	32
4. OVERALL PLANT LAYOUT	36
4.1 OPERATING CONCEPT.....	36
4.1.1 Main Operation Modes	37
4.1.2 Secondary Operation Modes.....	44
4.1.3 Simulative Only Operation Modes	47
4.2 OVERALL PLANT LAYOUT.....	51
5. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK	57

List of Figures

Figure 1: Sketch of POLYPHEM prototype concept from an early stage of the project development	9
Figure 2: Classification of the tasks (shown in green) related to this report in the context of the work package	10
Figure 3: THEMIS Solar Tower R&D Facility in the Eastern Pyrenees, France	12
Figure 4: Position of Mini Pegase Aperture (level 1) and Pegase aperture (level 2) at THEMIS Tower (photo: M. Karl)	12
Figure 5: Location of the THEMIS Solar Tower R&D Facility in the Eastern Pyrenees in Southern France	13
Figure 6: Visualisation of the available DNI	14
Figure 7: Number of hours as a function of the DNI range	14
Figure 8: Exemplary DNI values for four selected days (location of Odeillo, derived from Meteonorm)	15
Figure 9: Average ambient temperature for exemplary months of the weather data.	16
Figure 10: Visualization of the THEMIS ray tracing model, with detailed views of one heliostat with 9 sub-facets and the POLYPHEM absorber module at the backside of the MINI-PEGASE cavity	17
Figure 11: Sankey diagrams for full heliostat field efficiency and losses for three cases: a) absorbing cavity side panes; b) diffusely reflecting cavity side panes; c) specularly reflecting cavity side panes	17
Figure 12: Heliostat efficiencies for summer solstice at solar noon for the case with absorbing cavity side panes	18
Figure 13: Examples of solar receiver designs containing independent modules.	20
Figure 14: Details of the inner parts of the solar receiver modules.	21
Figure 15: Actual material selection for the POLYPHEM solar receiver module manufacturing.	22
Figure 16: Pictures of a solar receiver module representative mock-up made using HIP process.	22
Figure 17: KAEFER design for Garrett GTP 30-51 manifold	23
Figure 18: Exemplary scheme of working principle of POLYPHEM gas turbine	24
Figure 19: Turbine map	25
Figure 20: Garrett GTP 30-51 combustion chamber with manifold	25
Figure 21: KAEFER PICC reactor	26
Figure 22: Frequency converter topology	27
Figure 23: Recovery Heat Exchanger designed by AALBORG	28
Figure 24: Variation of main technical properties of Jarytherm® DBT with temperature.	30
Figure 25: Simulated temperature profile evolution from a fully charged tank (conducted by CIEMAT)	31
Figure 26: Simplified schematic of the Efficiency PACK ORC cycle	33
Figure 27: The ORC cycle and its dimension	33
Figure 28: ORC Cycle calculation results for thermal oil heat input	34
Figure 29: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Solar driven μ GT + Storage charging"	38
Figure 30: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Solar driven μ GT + Storage charging"	39
Figure 31: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Solar driven μ GT + ORC"	41
Figure 32: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Solar driven μ GT + ORC"	42
Figure 33: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Storage driven ORC"	43
Figure 34: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Storage driven ORC"	44
Figure 35: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Thermocline management 1"	46
Figure 36: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Thermocline management 2"	47
Figure 37: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Increased Storage charging"	49
Figure 38: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Electrical Storage Charging"	50
Figure 39: Initial version of the process flow diagram	51
Figure 40: Intermediate version of the process flow diagram introducing two separated oil cycles	52
Figure 41: Final Version of the process flow diagram including instrumentation (at the editorial deadline of this report)	56

List of Tables

Table 1: Table 2: Summary of Boundary Conditions at THEMIS R&D Facility	13
Table 3: Main weather parameters from Meteonorm for “THEMIS solar tower”, France, and summary of the reference conditions.	15
Table 4: Heliostat field characteristics relevant for the POLYPHEM plant design	16
Table 5: Main boundary conditions for the designing the receiver.	19
Table 6: Main parameters of the design of the solar receiver	20
Table 7: Recent results of thermos-hydraulic simulations concerning internal geometry influence on total pressure drop and maximum insulated wall temperature	21
Table 8: Final design data of the gas turbine	23
Table 9: Working parameters of recovery heat exchanger	28
Table 10: Main properties of Jarytherm® DBT	29
Table 11: Primary characteristics of the concrete formulations	31
Table 12: Technical specification of TES-System	32
Table 13: Technical specification of the modified ORC-System	35
Table 14: Overview of planned operation modes	36
Table 15: Overview of the simulation results for “Solar driven μ GT+ Storage charging”	39
Table 16: Overview of the simulation results for “Solar driven μ GT+ ORC”	42
Table 17: Overview of the simulation results for "Storage driven ORC"	44
Table 18: Comparison of “two oil-cycles” versus “one oil-cycle”	53
Table 19: Comparison of “exhaust downstream” versus “two oil-cycles”	53
Table 20: Consideration of economizer for the ORC	54
Table 21: Summary of System Specifications from POLYPHEM Proposal	57

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
μGT	Micro gas turbine
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation or Direct Normal Irradiance
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HAZOP	Hazard and operability (study)
KAE	Kaefer Isoliertechnik GmbH
M	Month
MS	Milestone
OM	Operation mode
ORC	‘Orcan Energy AG’ or ‘Organic Rankine Cycle’
PU	Public
RHX	Recovery heat exchanger
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

As described in Figure 1, the overall concept underpinning the POLYPHEM project is to bridge together two thermodynamic cycles with an intermediate storage system to make a combined cycle with unique flexibility. In this way, three innovative ideas bear the POLYPHEM concept:

- Coupling a small-scale organic Rankine cycle (ORC) with an open Brayton cycle (μ GT) to make a novel kind of combined cycle
- Integrating a low-cost thermal energy storage (TES) between both cycles
- Integrating a high temperature solar receiver in the top cycle

Figure 1: Sketch of POLYPHEM prototype concept from an early stage of the project development

The resulting concept is a hybrid solar-driven combined cycle featuring a small-scale CSP plant of next generation, consisting of a top cycle and bottom cycle (see Figure 1). Competing technologies featuring steam cycles are not suitable for small scale power generation with high conversion efficiency and limited water consumption. Five technology bricks are integrated to form the complete system: the solar field and receiver, the hybrid solar-driven micro gas-turbine, the thermal energy storage system, the organic Rankine cycle, and the control and regulation system.

This report describes the developing process to identify the overall plant layout and characterizes the final outcome. The developing process was an iterative process which required a regular exchange between the involved project parties and had a lot of steps in between.

Structure of the report:

- Chapter 1: Gives an introduction of the POLYPHEM project
- Chapter 2: States the boundary conditions of the site for the prototype which are relevant for the design of the components and the overall plant layout

- Chapter 3: Describes the design of the main components (sub-components)
- Chapter 4: Explains the operating concept of the plant and portrays the overall plant layout

The chapters, especially 3 and 4, should not be considered consecutively but rather in parallel, since the overall plant layout, the operation concept and the system specification of the main components are strongly co-dependent and accordingly in such a way developed.

1.1 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Decentralized power generation with heating/cooling and other applications capabilities will provide energy services to houses in remote areas and thereby addresses a main societal challenge: the need for more decarbonized energy. The purpose is to meet the variable demand of energy of a mini-grid. A POLYPHEM-like power plant is a combined cycle plant intended to be used for decentralized and sustainable small-scale power generation in the range of 40 kW to 2000 kW in remote areas.

The main challenges during the implementation of the POLYPHEM project are the design, component development and manufacturing, and the implementation and testing of the prototype plant. Within this work package, the overall plant layout of the POLYPHEM prototype has been developed and determined. Additionally, the individual components parameters have been specified. And finally, all the defined components are integrated into a static system model in a simulation environment in order to calculate the state of the working media at design condition and adjust the component specifications if necessary. This work serves as a basis for the following basic engineering of the prototype plant and the control system.

1.2 OBJECTIVES AND TASKS

Figure 2: Classification of the tasks (shown in green) related to this report in the context of the work package

Within the framework of the POLYPHEM Project a variety of novel components are being developed. The core components are:

- Solar receiver with pressurized air
- Hybrid solar-driven micro gas-turbine (solar and fuel powered)
- Recovery heat exchanger (transferring thermal energy from exhaust air to the thermal oil (Jarytherm DBT))
- One-tank stratified thermal energy storage (thermocline) with filler material
- ORC-system accepting hot thermal oil as heat source

The main task is to bring these sub-components into alignment and develop an overall design of the prototype plant which allows for efficient employment of the sub-components. Therefore, the technical specifications of the single components (e.g. size, temperatures, mass flow, power etc.) have to be developed with regard to the boundary conditions and the desired functionality of the prototype.

The plant

Furthermore, the plant is expected to provide a certain range of operation flexibility in order to be able to deliver electricity on demand 24/7. Therefore, a variety of operation modes are required in order to operate the plant under different conditions in regard to power production and the state of storage and other components. These operation modes and range of functions of the prototype plant influence the technical specifications of the single-components and the overall plant layout. Therefore, the operation modes had to be defined and evaluated in terms of feasibility within the boundary conditions of the project and considered which functions can be implemented.

Since the existing Heliostat field of the Themis plant will be used for the prototype, there is no need to design a new solar field. However, the existing field would be an oversized field for the prototype and the required Heliostats have to be selected in order to limit the radiation flux on the receiver to the maximum allowed by the air receiver.

The solar receiver specifications had to be determined in close collaboration with the micro gas-turbine and the recovery heat exchanger since they form the core components of the top cycle. The gas turbine set is composed of commercially available components which allows the compressed air to be heated up by the solar receiver as well as by the innovative combustion chamber (KAEFER PICC technology)

The basic specification of the recovery heat exchanger is determined based on static simulation results. The thermal energy storage bridges the top cycle and the bottom cycle and had to be aligned to both (see Figure 1). The ORC cycle is a commercially available system which is modified according to the HTF and temperature level of the POLYPHEM project.

Within this task (in cooperation with other work packages), specifications of the specific component or sub-system listed above are derived. The design of the sub-components is performed by means of numerical calculations or simulation models / software tools.

Based on the information available and with the support of other grant recipients, different possible plant layouts have been assessed and the final technical layout of the complete prototype plant is iteratively derived. This includes the dimensions of the interfaces between the sub-systems. Feedback was provided to the respective tasks dealing with detailed component design.

For different potential plant layouts, plant operating strategies have been developed with the support from other project partners. For steady states of the operation modes, heat and mass balances have been calculated by means of EBSILON® Professional modelling software.

2. BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF THE PROTOTYPE SITE

The POLYPHEM prototype plant will be set up at the THEMIS Solar Tower R&D Facility in the Eastern Pyrenees, France – operated by CNRS. The heliostat field of the THEMIS solar tower will be available for experimental operation, the receiver of the POLYPHEM prototype will be installed behind the former *mini-pegase* 1.65 m x 1.65 m aperture. All components of the prototype “Hybrid Solar Micro Gas Turbine” part will be

installed at a platform behind the mini-pegase aperture at 80 m above ground. The remaining components of the prototype will be installed at the ground level close to the tower base.

Figure 3: THEMIS Solar Tower R&D Facility in the Eastern Pyrenees, France¹

Figure 4: Position of Mini Pegase Aperture (level 1) and Pegase aperture (level 2) at THEMIS Tower (photo: M. Karl)

¹ Wikimedia Commons contributors, "File:THEMIS-P1010369.JPG," Wikimedia Commons, the free media repository, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=File:THEMIS-P1010369.JPG&oldid=76855844> (accessed July 16, 2019).

Figure 5: Location of the THEMIS Solar Tower R&D Facility in the Eastern Pyrenees in Southern France²

Table 1: Table 2: Summary of Boundary Conditions at THEMIS R&D Facility

Boundary Conditions		
Coordinates - center of solar field	42.50256 Latitude [°N] , 1.97501 Longitude [°E]	[°]
Geographic elevation above mean sea level – tower base	1634	m
Geographic elevation above mean sea level – “mini-pegase” receiver aperture	1715	m
Height of Polyphem receiver / micro gas turbine / RHEX above ground	81	m

2.1 WEATHER DATA

Information about the weather is essential for the performance assessment of a CSP plant and for the definition of the design boundary conditions. The available direct normal irradiance (DNI) in W/m² defines the amount of produced power. The design value of DNI defines the size of the solar field and the size of the solar receiver according to the expected performance of these two components. Moreover, the POLYPHEM system includes an open cycle gas turbine whose performance is directly linked to the ambient conditions such as ambient pressure and temperature. Therefore, the following paragraphs give a short summary of the main performance parameters and the weather input data used for this study.

The general DNI pattern is shown in Figure 6 for a location about 12 km away from the THEMIS testing facility. Plotting the DNI for every day of the year, it is visible that during the winter months there are less hours of solar irradiance than in summer. However, the DNI values for this location are also acceptable during winter months. In Figure 8 four exemplarily DNI curves for four different days in a year are shown in more detail.

² map data: © OpenStreetMap contributors, SRTM | map style: © OpenTopoMap (CC-BY-SA)

The DNI profiles for the four days show significant differences over the year and depending on the day chosen. The DNI profile for the 1st of June is an example for a day with bad DNI values e.g. supposedly due to clouds. The profiles for the days in January, March and September are days with good DNI values. Going from winter to summer months there is the clear shift in the amount of hours with sunshine (as typical for France in the northern hemisphere). In September there are about four hours more between sunrise and sunset.

Table 3 summarizes the main parameters for the location according to the weather data from Meteonorm³

Figure 6: Visualisation of the available DNI

for the location “THEMIS solar tower”. The data is available in the TMY3 format from Meteonorm. The annual Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI) is 2084.6 kWh/m²/yr. For the design of the system a reference Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) of 900 W/m² has been chosen. Figure 7 shows the number of hours as a function of the DNI range in a bar chart. As it can be seen, the DNI range of 900-1000 W/m² is the most frequent range. The reference ambient temperature is 15 °C in accordance with the ISO standard reference conditions and the reference ambient pressure is 0.83 bar, accounting for the elevated altitude of the THEMIS testing facility.

Figure 7: Number of hours as a function of the DNI range

³ AG, M., 2015. Meteonorm: Irradiation data for every place on Earth. Available at: <https://meteonorm.com>
Overall Plant Layout - POLYPHEM_WP4_D4.1

Table 3: Main weather parameters from Meteonorm for “THEMIS solar tower”, France, and summary of the reference conditions.

	Value	Unit	Comment
Coordinates	42.501	°N	Latitude
	1.974	°E	Longitude
Altitude (gas turbine)	1715	m a.s.l	Elevation above mean sea level
Annual Direct Normal Irradiation (DNI)	2084.6	kWh/m ² /y	-
Minimum temperature	- 9.9	°C	on 15.02.2005
Maximum temperature	25.3	°C	on 21.07.2005
Maximal Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI)	1025	W/m ²	on 06.05.2005
Reference Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI)	900	W/m ²	Used for system design
Reference ambient temperature	15	°C	ISO standard reference condition
Reference ambient pressure	0.83	bar	-

Figure 8: Exemplary DNI values for four selected days (location of Odeillo, derived from Meteonorm)

Figure 9: Average ambient temperature for exemplary months of the weather data.

3. SUB COMPONENTS

This chapter describes the main components of the POLYPHEM plant and their final design.

3.1 HELIOSTAT FIELD

The existing THEMIS heliostat field together with the existing tower structure will be used within the project. The relevant main characteristics of the heliostat field are provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Heliostat field characteristics relevant for the POLYPHEM plant design

Characteristic	Value	Unit
Number of heliostats	107	-
Mirror area of one heliostat	54.1	m ²
Total mirror area	5789	m ²

The solar power needed to drive the gas-turbine in solar-only operation mode is much lower than the potential power delivered by the entire solar field. Depending on the optical efficiency of the heliostat field and on the thermal efficiency of the solar receiver, only a small number of heliostats will be used for the needs of the project POLYPHEM. In practice, about 25 heliostats located in the central zone of the field will eventually serve in the project. To get an impression of the heliostat field's efficiency and the required number of heliostats, the ray tracing simulation as set up in WP7 has been used for an assessment (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: Visualization of the THEMIS ray tracing model, with detailed views of one heliostat with 9 sub-facets and the POLYPHEM absorber module at the backside of the MINI-PEGASE cavity

Based on the model, an assessment of the field’s efficiency and optical losses for summer solstice at solar noon has been performed. Three different cases regarding the optical properties of the cavity side panes have been studied, for which results are presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Sankey diagrams for full heliostat field efficiency and losses for three cases: a) absorbing cavity side panes; b) diffusely reflecting cavity side panes; c) specularly reflecting cavity side panes

While the field efficiency can be increased with reflecting cavity side panes, the overall efficiency is rather low, mainly due to very strong spillage. This can be explained due to the comparatively small test cavity aperture opening of 1.65 m x 1.65 m (The heliostat field was originally designed for a significantly larger cavity above the one used in the POLYPHEM project). Thus, if the cavity will have side panes of significant depths, it is recommended to use reflective surfaces, to avoid the need for active cooling. The present cavity is 1.2 m x 1.2 m, surrounded by water-cooled side panes that fill the gap between the cavity and the aperture in the tower. Additional spillage (outside the aperture) is managed with passive protective shields (metallic radiant shields).

Overall, a simple estimation with $DNI = 900 \text{ W/m}^2$, heliostat field mirror area $A_{HSF} = 5191 \text{ m}^2$ and optical efficiency $\eta_{opt} > 19 \%$ yields for the available absorbed power

$$P_{abs} = DNI \cdot A_{HSF} \cdot \eta_{opt} > 850 \text{ kW}$$

Thus, even for the absolute worst case scenario, the heliostat field will be able to provide sufficiently large absorbed power for the specifications of the POLYPHEM receiver. Figure 12 shows the heliostat efficiency distribution in the field. Clearly, the central heliostats close to the tower are vastly more efficient than the rest, partly more than an order of magnitude. Consequently, the optical efficiency of a central sub-group of heliostats will be significantly higher than for the entire field (around 40 % estimated based on Figure 12). Thus, it is expected that the required power can be provided with a relatively small sub-group of the heliostats. The optical ray tracing assessment for a central selection of heliostats will be performed later on, to support the yield prediction of the system.

Figure 12: Heliostat efficiencies for summer solstice at solar noon for the case with absorbing cavity side panes

3.2 TOP CYCLE: AIR BRAYTON CYCLE

The top cycle of the combined cycle power plant consists of the solar receiver and combustor as heat sources and the gas turbine set with compressor, turbine, gear box, generator and other periphery. The waste heat of top cycle is transferred to the bottom cycle via HRX.

3.2.1 Solar Receiver

The solar receiver design and material choice (surface in contact with high temperature air) are linked to the WP1 of the POLYPHEM project.

The solar receiver design is related to the task 1.2 of the project. The design of the solar receiver is directly linked to the specifications of the micro-gas turbine. Table 5 summarizes the main boundary conditions for the designing the receiver.

Table 5: Main boundary conditions for the designing the receiver.

Characteristic	Value	Unit
Temperature air inlet	190	°C
Temperature air outlet	750	°C
Pressure air inlet (inside tubes)	3.32	bar
Air mass flowrate	820	g/s
Net heat flux	500	kW/m ²
Maximum allowed Pressure drop	170	mbar

Thermo-hydraulic simulations have been made in order to comply with the parameters mentioned in Table 5. The last ones permitted to establish most of the receiver module details (global receiver size, number of tubes inside, number of tube rows). However, other detailed parameters such as number of modules, thickness of the inserts (twisted tapes), and the parameter H (rotation period) are given in this documents as well, according to the last discussions between CEA and CNRS.

Two examples of solar receiver designs containing independent modules are presented in Figure 13. In these cases, the modules are directly welded on the inlet and outlet tubes that connect the micro-gas turbine with the receiver.

Figure 13: Examples of solar receiver designs containing independent modules.

At the date of this deliverable, the design points that are already fixed are listed in table 5:

Table 6: Main parameters of the design of the solar receiver

Part	Value	Unit
Number of modules	4	-
Insulated length of the solar receiver	1000	mm
Insulated width of the solar receiver	1200	mm
Height of the solar receiver (active part)	84	mm
Number of tubes in a row	108	-
Number of rows	7	-
Tube inner diameter	6	mm
Tube outer diameter	8	mm
Copper thickness between two tubes in a row	3	mm
Copper thickness between two rows of tubes	3	mm
Copper thickness between the protective layer and the first row of tubes	1.5	mm
Ni base alloy thickness at the exposed face	2	mm
Inlet tube (manifold) diameter	150	mm
Outlet tube (manifold) diameter	200	mm

All the fixed parameters and those that have to be defined are summarized on the schematic representation of a 6 modules solar receiver on Figure 14.

Figure 14: Details of the inner parts of the solar receiver modules.

Recent thermo-hydraulic simulations show that the insert geometry highly influences the overall pressure drop while the maximum temperature of the insulated wall is less affected.

Further simulations are planned in the next months to fix the insert geometry including complementary parameters like solar emissivity on the surfaces and more precise thermal exchange coefficients.

Table 7: Recent results of thermos-hydraulic simulations concerning internal geometry influence on total pressure drop and maximum insulated wall temperature

Width of the receiver (mm)	Number of tube rows	Horizontal space between tubes (mm)	Thickness of inserts d (mm)	Rotation period H (mm)	Ratio H/d	Pressure drop (mbar)	T max wall (°C)
1200	7	3	0.8	30	5	126	995

3.2.2 Solar receiver modules material selection and manufacturing process

As the task 1.1 dedicated to the material selection is delayed to the end of year 2019, the final choice is not made. However, the actual results show that the solar receiver would be manufactured using two nickel base alloys, alloy 600 and alloy 230. In a first approach, the alloy 230 would be used for the parts exposed to the highest temperature (insulated surface and lateral faces) and/or to the inner gas pressure (manifolds). The alloy 600 would be employed for the opposite surface to the insulated one, for inner tubes and for the tube inserts. In all cases, the copper alloy will be high purity copper grade Cu-OF (ISO reference). The actual material references for manufacturing the solar receiver modules are presented on the Figure 15.

Figure 15: Actual material selection for the POLYPHEM solar receiver module manufacturing.

The manufacturing process that will be used for the solar receiver modules is diffusion bonding carried out in a hot isostatic pressure furnace. Diffusion bonding or diffusion welding is a solid-state welding technique used in metalworking, capable of joining similar and dissimilar metals. It enforces plasticity and creep deformation of the metallic parts combined with solid-state atomic diffusion. Diffusion bonding is usually implemented by applying high temperature combined with high pressure (typically 1000 °C/1000 bar).

To manufacture the solar receiver modules, diffusion bonding is made using Hot Isostatic Pressing (HIP) process. The HIP process subjects a component to both elevated temperature and isostatic gas pressure in a high pressure containment vessel. The pressurizing gas most widely used is argon. The chamber is heated, causing the pressure inside the vessel to increase. Many systems use associated gas pumping to achieve the necessary pressure level. Pressure is applied to the material from all directions.

Figure 16 presents pictures of a representative mock-up of a solar receiver module manufactured by HIP process. This mock-up is made of copper and stainless steel.

Figure 16: Pictures of a solar receiver module representative mock-up made using HIP process.

3.2.3 Micro gas turbine

From M1 to M14 KAEFER followed two different ways for provision of the POLYPHEM gas turbine. The choice of the gas turbine and its inherent specification had an influence on the overall plant layout.

To ensure the project progress and to minimize risks, KAEFER purchased a used Garret GTP30. This machine type is known to be suitable, as it combines following features:

- Electric power range 30 – 100 kW
- Accessibility of compressor discharge air for solarization purposes
- Exhaust temperatures suited for heat recovery (< 700 °C)

For connection of external heat sources (combustor, solar receiver) a manifold has been designed. Figure 17 shows the design of this manifold.

Figure 17: KAEFER design for Garrett GTP 30-51 manifold

The GTP 30-51 (as all Garrett micro gas turbines from that model series) has been designed for the aviation sector (light weight, high performance) which results in following disadvantages:

- Machine itself and all spare parts are relatively expensive
- Machine is designed for relatively short service times and high maintenance
- Supply of spare parts is time consuming

For these reasons, from the beginning of the project, KAEFER also investigated the option of providing a micro gas turbine made of commercially available and much more robust components (see example in Figure 18). A company manufacturing turbo equipment was selected to supply components from serial production. A solution optimized for the project was designed. The selected components are usually applied at marine propulsion application, so the components are extremely robust and designed for long meantime to maintenance.

The relevant compressor/ turbine maps were identified, and the design pressure ratio was found to be 4. Compared to the GTP 30-51 (pressure ratio of 2.4), the flow velocity is significantly reduced, which facilitates the design of the solar receiver and of the recovery heat exchanger downstream with appropriate pressure losses.

It was agreed with FRAUNHOFER ISE, CNRS, CEA and AALBORG to continue the project with a tailor-made gas turbine featuring new process parameters (shown in Table 8).

Table 8: Final design data of the gas turbine

Description	Value	Unit
Turbine mass flowrate	0.82	kg/s
Compression ratio	4	-
Compressor discharge pressure at Thémis (absolute)	3.32	bar

Compressor discharge temperature at Thémis	190	°C
Turbine inlet temperature (Receiver outlet temperature)	750	°C
Turbine outlet temperature (RHX inlet temperature)	495	°C
Considered ambient temperature in Thémis	15	°C
Considered ambient pressure in Thémis	830	hPa
Considered altitude at Thémis	1715	m
Maximum targeted pressure loss within solar receiver	170	mbar
Compressor isentropic efficiency	0.79	-
Turbine isentropic efficiency	0.86	-
Nominal electric output of the generator	76.5	kW

Figure 18: Exemplary scheme of working principle of POLYPHEM gas turbine ⁴

The entire gen-set (turbine, gear-boxes, and generator) will be placed on a tailor-made skid. This system enables pre-assembly of the entire gen-set in Bremen to reduce installation effort in Themis.

⁴ ABB, 2011. ABB Library - VTR. Available at: <https://search-ext.abb.com/library/Download.aspx?DocumentID=VTR&LanguageCode=en&DocumentPartId=&Action=Launch>
 Overall Plant Layout - POLYPHEM_WP4_D4.1

Figure 19: Turbine map

3.2.4 Combustion Chamber

Originally it was planned to use the diesel driven combustion chamber that belongs to the Garrett GTP 30-51, which was bought for this project. To enable connection of the combustion chamber to the interconnection tubing, a special manifold has been designed (shown in Figure 20).

Figure 20: Garrett GTP 30-51 combustion chamber with manifold

This Diesel combustor (as all flame-based combustors) enables full load operation and power throttle to approximately 30 % of nominal power. Decreasing the amount of injected fuel to less than 30 % leads to flame extinction as diesel atomization does not take place properly, respectively the flame is blown-off by the air flow. Although this combustion chamber would fulfil the requirements of this project, it does not

cover the power range from 0 - 30 %. This power range is very significant for CSP plants as it reflects the power gap which is caused by clouds passing by and start-up/ shut-down operation in the morning/ at evening. Therefore, it was brought into agreement with FISE, CNRS, CEA and AALBORG CSP to replace the above-mentioned combustion chamber by a flame-less catalytic combustor developed by KAEFER within the recent years, named PICC⁵ shown in Figure 21:

Figure 21: KAEFER PICC reactor

It can be operated with any common gas (propane, butane) and throttled to any required power output, so it covers the range which is significant for CSP plants. It is an existing technology developed by KAEFER, all rights stay exclusively at KAEFER.

3.2.5 Generator

KAEFER has specified and purchased an electric generator that matches with this project specific requirements:

- Suitable to be operated as starter and as generator (in connection with suitable frequency converter)
- Electric power: up to 75 kW
- Hardened version for operation within complicated climate conditions as expected in Thémis test site (increased humidity and ambient temperature)
- Heating device to prevent from damage due to changing climate
- Equipped with multiple sensors for temperature and vibration (important for gas turbine monitoring)
- Casing design type (shaft, connection dimension) to enable replacement by standard machine for commercial case

3.2.6 Frequency Converter

Feeding of electric energy into the local electrical grid in Thémis is accompanied by a couple of restrictions (approval permit request, energy feeding forecast). For this reason, a tailor-made frequency converter is required that combines following properties:

- FC capable to be connected to electric grid for power consumption (start-up procedure of turbine)
- Connection of load bank for conversion of electric energy to thermal heat
- FC shall be similar to (later) commercial FC that feeds electrical energy to grid (commercial case)

⁵ Name registered for patent approval.

Figure 22: Frequency converter topology

The system is composed of various individual components (see Figure 22):

- Line filter: electronic filter that is placed between the AC power line and the equipment to attenuate electromagnetic interference between the electrical grid and the equipment.
- Base line module: Controls the power flow from the grid to the DC Bus.
- AC/CD converter: Only one power direction possible, from the grid to the DC bus
- Intermediate circuit to buffer electric energy and decouple the grid, the motor module and the brake module. Consists of a capacitor and a DC power rail.
- Motor module: controls the speed of the generator by controlling the torque of the generator. Depending on the direction of the torque the machine acts as a motor or a generator. Finally, the electric power flow takes place bidirectional.
 - Motor: Power flow from DC bus to the machine
 - Generator: Power flow from machine to the DC bus
- Brake module: Controls the amount of energy that is buffered in the DC bus capacity. If the amount of energy, which is represented by the voltage of the capacitor, reaches a certain level the brake modules activates an energy flow from the DC bus to the brake resistance.
- Brake resistance: Resistive power load. Works as power sink. The electric energy is converted into heat to avoid an energy overload in the DC bus capacitor.

The above listed items are a result of extensive engineering and discussions with FISE and CNRS that took place between M1 and M18. KAEFER has started to request local specialist companies (with respective certifications) to offer the entire assembled system that fulfils valid regulatory requirements.

3.3 RECOVERY HEAT EXCHANGER: CONNECTING TOP AND BOTTOM CYCLE

The recovery heat exchanger represents the connecting point between the air cycle and the oil cycle. Thermal energy from the exhaust gas flow is transferred to the oil cycle providing heat to charge the TES or run the ORC.

A preliminary air/oil heat exchanger was developed based on the preliminary μ GT data received from KAEFER. Material quality and design details were selected by AALBORG, considering the highest possible efficiency with respect to the pressure loss restriction on the air side.

Calculation showed that extended heating surface area on the air side is required to optimize the efficiency. Investigations showed that highest possible fin density (fin per meter) would give the best efficiency/price ratio. Normal high frequency welded fin can be made with a maximum amount of 275 fins per meter. Newest manufacturing technology using laser welding can reach 300 fins per meter, which is selected. Pipe material was selected as P235GH, which is a normal pressure pipe material in the EN standard. Higher alloy materials are not required, as the oil temperature is relatively low (300 °C). As the air inlet temperature can increase up to 590 °C, the fin material needs to be high alloy or stainless steel. Stainless steel is selected as the air temperature can be higher during some μ GT load cases.

In an advanced stage of the project KAEFER changed the μ GT model (see 3.2.3), which resulted in new air outlet data and new requirements for maximum pressure loss. AALBORG CSP redesigned the heat exchanger based on the new data (see Figure 23). The pipe and fin materials are unchanged.

Calculations of the overall plant (see chapter 4) revealed that the originally assumed thermal load was too little and the heat exchanger had to be scaled up a little.

Figure 23: Recovery Heat Exchanger designed by AALBORG

The main working parameters of the heat exchanger can be taken from the following table:

Table 9: Working parameters of recovery heat exchanger

Description	Value	Unit
Thermal output	≈ 305	kW
Tube Side (thermal oil)		
Design pressure	17	bar(a)
Design outlet temperature	350	°C
Mass flow rate	0.6	kg/s
Fouling factor	0	m ² *K/W
Pressure loss	2281	mbar
Shell Side (gas)		
Design temperature	495	°C
Mass flow rate	0.82	kg/s
Fouling factor	0	m ² *K/W
Absolute humidity	5	g/kg
Pressure loss	2.21	mbar

3.4 BOTTOM CYCLE: THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE AND ORC-PROCESS

The bottom cycle of the combined cycle power plant consists primarily of the thermal energy storage and the ORC. It is supplied with thermal energy from the RHX. Oil is used as a heat transfer fluid to connect the components.

3.4.1 Heat Transfer Fluid

Based on the fact that it does not require any over pressure within the desired temperature range in the primary and secondary oil cycle Jarytherm® DBT⁶ has been chosen as heat transfer fluid (HTF). This is a result of discussions between the project members. Jarytherm® DBT is a 100 % synthetic HTF that is especially suitable for heating under atmospheric pressure between 250 °C – 350 °C, with an operating range from 0 °C to 350 °C. Moreover, it is characterized by a well-defined composition and a low cold viscosity which is interesting for start-up of the plant. The main technical properties are summarized in Table 10. A visual summary of the main properties and their temperature dependent behavior is given in Figure 24. Another advantage of Jarytherm® DBT is the low toxicity of the original fluid and the potential degradation products. One important aspect for the overall design of the prototype plant is the fact that Jarytherm® DBT requires an inert atmosphere without oxygen, thus all vessels in which the oil will be stored have to be equipped with a nitrogen injecting system.

Table 10: Main properties of Jarytherm® DBT

	Value	Unit
Composition	Blend of Dibenzyltoluene isomers	-
Flash point	200	°C
Fire point	230	°C
Auto-ignition temperature	470	°C
Pour point	-34	°C
Boiling point	390	°C
Minimum temperature in use	0	°C
Maximum temperature in use	350 (bulk) 370 (film)	°C
Kinematic viscosity	50 (at 20 °C) 0.45 (at 300 °C)	mm ² /s
Density	1044 (at 20 °C) 836 (at 300 °C)	kg/m ³
Specific heat capacity	1.584 (at 20 °C) 2.477 (at 300 °C)	kJ/kg.K

⁶ Arkema, January 2018. Jarytherm - Heat Transfer Fluids. Available at: <https://www.arkema.com/en/products/product-finder/range-viewer/Jarytherm-heat-transfer-fluids/?t=2>
Overall Plant Layout - POLYPHEM_WP4_D4.1

Figure 24: Variation of main technical properties of Jarytherm® DBT with temperature.

3.4.2 Thermal Energy Storage

The main aim of the thermal storage development, which is conducted by CIEMAT and ARRAELA S.A., is to identify a cost effective solution to store large amounts of thermal energy. State-of-the-art thermal energy storage systems consist mainly of two-tank configurations storing the hot and cold media respectively. They are made of metallic walls and require rather sophisticated foundations with insulation layers. In order to drive down capital costs of the storage system the proposed thermal storage solution for the POLYPHEM project consists of a single tank solution with filler material, concrete walls and concrete-only foundations. Using cost effective filler material within the tank reduces the amount of HTF needed. In the single tank both the hot and cold media is being stored applying thermal stratification. The thermal boundary layer between the hot and cold media is called thermocline. The thinner this zone can be adjusted the better is the thermal storage efficiency, since a large volume of the tank has a homogenous temperature (either hot or cold) resulting in higher exergetic efficiencies.

A thermofluid analysis has been performed to assess the influence of the number and size of inlet and outlet connections. The velocity of the oil in the loop is slow, and it is very slow inside the tank. In all conditions, including central position and low number of inlet and outlet oil connection points, the thickness of the thermocline region is expected to remain very stable and occupies approximately 25 % of the height of the tank (see Figure 25). After a number of charge and discharge cycles the thermocline zone is expected to grow, which would lead to a reduced storage capacity. Hence, counter measures regarding the operation concept and overall design have to be taken, the so called “thermocline management” (see also 4.1.2.2).

Figure 25: Simulated temperature profile evolution from a fully charged tank (conducted by CIEMAT)

The approach is to implement a non-pressurized tank made of concrete and to promote the utilization of concrete for insulating foundation. These approaches are expected to be effective solutions for solving the limitation in size imposed by metallic storage tanks and expanded clay aggregate spheres as insulation material for the foundations.

The main materials involved in the storage system are the thermal oil used as heat transfer fluid (HTF), the solid filler, a concrete formulation for the tank walls and a concrete formulation for the tank foundations. Long term compatibility tests with cycling temperatures for the thermal oil (see 3.4.1) and potential materials as well as material characterization have been conducted to determine the materials for the TES system of the prototype. The oil analysis has revealed negligible differences after cycle tests. The driving parameter used to assign material to each application is the thermal conductivity. Potential candidates for the concrete formulations and the outcomes of the elemental analysis are show in the following table:

Table 11: Primary characteristics of the concrete formulations

	HEATEK-AC	HEATEC-RC	HEATEC-RV
Main Characteristics	Granular material: Natural (magnetite, including FeO content)	Granular material: non-metallic urban wastes	Granular material: metallic wastes from blast furnaces
Density [kg/m ³]	3925	2040	3105
Specific heat in [kJ/(kgK)]	n/a	1.7 – 2.6	0.75 – 1.25
Volumetric capacity [(kJ/m ³ K)]	n/a	≈ 4386	≈ 3027
Heat conductivity [(W/mK)]	n/a	0.6 – 0.1	1.0 – 1.2
Cost factor	10/1	1/1	1/1

The tank walls and the foundations are reinforced with steel bars. A free volume over the thermal oil must be considered for the nitrogen atmosphere in the tank. The design height of this free volume is set at 0.2 m. The main parameters of the storage system are summarized in the following table:

Table 12: Technical specification of TES-System

Description	Value	Unit
Design oil mass flow	0.7	kg/s
Tank wall, lid & filler material	HEATEK-RV	-
Tank insulation slab	HEATEK-RC	-
Inner tank diameter	2.6	m
Total tank height	3.2	m
Tank wall thickness	0.5	m
Tank lid thickness	0.4	m
Mass of filler material	≈ 29	t
Oil volume in tank	6300	l
Tank porosity	0.4	-
Effective thermal capacity	2000	kWh
Overall thermal capacity	2600	kWh
Ratio of thermocline zone of the total volume of the tank	25	%

3.4.3 Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC)

For the ORC cycle, the second generation ORC from the efficiency PACK series of ORCAN ENERGY, which is modified for the purpose of this project, has been selected to be used for the POLYPHEM-Project.

Figure 26 shows the ORC system and its input and outputs. The evaporator transfers the heat into the efficiency PACK. Thereby, the pressurized working fluid (R1233zd) is heated and then routed to the expansion machine. The vaporized working fluid drives the expansion machine and thereby also the generator, producing electricity. The working fluid is condensed in the condenser, which releases residual heat into the ambient air. The now again liquid working fluid is brought to high pressure in the pump. This closes the cycle and it starts again.

Figure 26: Simplified schematic of the Efficiency PACK ORC cycle

The efficiency PACKs integrated in containers are easy to transport, can be installed quickly, are easy to connect, and can be switched on and off automatically. Figure 27 shows the compact ORC solution.

Figure 27: The ORC cycle and its dimension

In order to adapt the ORC system to the requirement of the POLYPHEM project, it has been investigated whether the efficiency Pack can deal with thermal oil as heat source instead of hot water, and if not, what modifications on the system will be required. As a result, the operating conditions of the ORC cycle were redefined based on the requirements resulting from the utilization of thermal oil as the heat transfer fluid.

The rising of the vapor temperature of the working fluid up to 140 °C and of the input temperature of the HTF up to 170 °C affects the operating parameters of the following components:

- The required integrity level temperature of the pipes for the heat transfer fluid
- The required integrity level temperature and pressure rating (from 22 bar(g) to 28 bar(g)) of the pipes for working fluid

Operating parameters of the expansion machine are also affected:

- The allowed inflow temperature
- The pressure rating of the expansion machine (high pressure side)

- The allowed temperature for the windings of the electric generator. The electric generator is hermetically coupled with the expansion machine and cooled by the vapor which is leaving the expansion machine on the low pressure side. To secure proper cooling numerical and experimental experiments have been carried out.

The ORC cycle has been modelled and simulated using a proprietary simulation tool (see Figure 28). The design parameters of the working fluid at different points in the cycle are shown in the screen shot below.

Figure 28: ORC Cycle calculation results for thermal oil heat input

Engineering of heat source for ORC (heat exchanger)

The current brazed plate heat exchangers (BPHE) are already suitable for the operation with thermal oil as heat source. Maximum operating parameters for structural integrity according to supplier specifications are:

- Max. temperature: 200 °C
- Max. pressure: 30 bar(g)
- Chemical compatibility with thermal oil is given

The simulation tool, which is provided by the supplier of the BPHE, is already capable of simulating the behavior of the component with thermal oil as heat input. By simulating the desired maximum operation point, obtained by the cycle calculations, it could be seen that the desired performance of W301 and D301 can be reached without modification of the component hardware.

Other modifications of the ORC pack

The current specification of the expansion machine already allows the operation with the new cycle parameters. However, validation tests are required to evaluate the performance and the durability under the new operating parameters.

The hot water circulation pump has been replaced by a model of KSB Etaline SYT, which is suitable for thermal oil up to 350 °C. In order to be able to control the mass flow of thermal oil through the evaporator for the test operation, it will be equipped with a frequency inverter to allow operation under variable speed.

The working fluid R245fa has been replaced by R1233zd, a working fluid from the group of the Hydrofluoroolefin which offers lower boiling pressures at the desired operating temperatures. Cycle simulation shows a slightly better cycle efficiency compared to R245fa, especially when it comes to higher condensing temperatures due to hot environment of the ORC system.

Table 13: Technical specification of the modified ORC-System

Description	Value	Unit
Working fluid	R1233zd	-
Maximal power output	25	kW
Minimal inlet temperature	140	°C
Maximal inlet temperature	330	°C
Maximal pressure of working fluid	28	bar(g)

4. OVERALL PLANT LAYOUT

4.1 OPERATING CONCEPT

In order to design the complete demonstration system at the Themis solar tower facility, the range of operation modes has a significant influence. Within this study, the focus was on the air and fluid cycles and assumed a fixed available thermal input onto the receiver, not taking the optical system into consideration. Due to the fixed budget conditions of the project framework and the given boundary conditions of the existing facility at Themis, in which the prototype will be integrated, an evaluation of the most significant operation modes and desired functionalities of the prototype was carried out. The aim was to distinguish between the most desired functionalities, taking research questions and the context of the grant agreement into account, and the functionalities/operation modes which can be rather demonstrated by simulation and have not to be implemented in reality for simplification and cost reduction measures. Other crucial aspects for the design of the complete system are risk mitigation and safety measures which have been identified in a hazard and operability study. The outcomes of this study were also fed back to the design process. In the following table the planned operation modes of the prototype and the simulated ones are listed. At this point additional considered states (e.g. cold / hot standby) and sequences (e.g. start-up, initial oil filling, regular / emergency shut-down) will not be elaborated on. However, these considerations have also had an influence on the overall system. The explanations within this chapter are mostly based on the final overall plant layout described in chapter 4.2.

Table 14: Overview of planned operation modes

	Name	Short description
Primary targets of the project	Solar driven μ GT and Storage charging	μ GT is driven by solar absorber at nominal load. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to the thermal energy storage to charge the TES for a shifted electricity production.
	Solar driven μ GT and ORC	μ GT is driven by solar absorber at nominal load. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to ORC for maximal electrical output of the plant.
	Storage driven ORC	Heat from the TES is used to run the ORC at times when the μ GT is not running.
Secondary targets of the project	Fuel driven μ GT and ORC	μ GT is driven by the combustor. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to ORC for maximal electrical output of plant.
	Thermocline management	At end of charging of TES the thermocline is pushed from bottom of tank to ORC to destroy thermocline and utilize the thermal energy stored in the thermocline At end of discharging, the thermocline is pushed to ORC to destroy thermocline and utilize the thermal energy stored in the thermocline.
	Solar driven μ GT and ORC and Storage charging	μ GT is driven by solar absorber. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, transferred to the secondary oil cycle and split between ORC and TES for

Simulated Only		a shifted electricity production and higher electrical output of the plant.
	Solar and Fuel driven μ GT	In case of insufficient DNI fuel is used in parallel to maintain full load of μ GT.
	Solar and Storage driven ORC	In case of insufficient DNI, additional energy from the storage is used to maintain full load of ORC.
	Increased Storage charging / “Max. thermal energy”	Harness solar energy for storage charging when there is no demand for electrical output of the plant: The turbine section of the μ GT is partly bypassed in order to reduce its electrical output and increase the exhaust temperature. Thus, the thermal power to charge the storage is increased.
	Electrical Storage Charging	The integrated electrical heater heats the oil for purposes of el. net stability or temperature maintenance.

Thermodynamic assessment

In order to assess the thermodynamic cycles of the system the software EBSILON® Professional has been used. It is a simulation tool for thermodynamic cycle processes that can be used for plant planning, design and optimization and offers a comprehensive component library. However, due to the iterative approach in the design of the POLYPHEM plant the developed EBSILON® models show some divergences towards the assumed final layout as presented in 0. Another aspect is that not all details of the final plant could be implemented one-to-one within the simulation. Nevertheless, these deviations are acceptable in the process of defining the most suitable rough layout of the system. The main task is to calculate the heat and mass balances of the cycles in order to identify the main parameters for the sub-components introduced in chapter 3 and the component interfaces in order to give rough dimensions for pipe diameters and insulation. The optical calculations and the resulting thermal power available at the solar receiver have not been calculated within the EBSILON® simulation. For these aspects detailed in-house calculation methods are available at Fraunhofer ISE. The stated pump power in the diagrams below will be reassessed in upcoming calculations. Another major deviation between the EBSILON® model and the *real* layout of the system is that within the EBSILON® model the TES is not considered to have solid fillers. Therefore, a stratified storage with a larger volume is being applied in the model in order to reach a storage capacity close to the actual capacity of the prototype.

4.1.1 Main Operation Modes

In this section the three main operation modes are described.

4.1.1.1 Solar driven μ GT and Storage charging

This is one of the main operation schemes during daytime with high DNI and normal electric power demand. The μ GT is driven by the solar absorber at highest possible capacity depending on the available flux on the receiver. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to the thermal energy storage to charge the TES for a shifted electricity production. This operation mode will be tested in the prototype plant as one of the main targets of the project.

The states of the main components are as follows:

- Solar receiver is at operation temperature
- Compressor / receiver / μ GT are at operation air volume flow; μ GT generator is producing power
- RHX is at operation temperature

- Primary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow
- Secondary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow to charge TES
- Valve at top of TES is open and hot oil is charging TES
- ORC is off

Figure 29 shows the state of the components and represents the flow direction within the plant for this operation mode.

Figure 29: Schematic diagram of operation mode “Solar driven μ GT + Storage charging”

Figure 30 depicts the results of the static simulation. It shows the state of the working media throughout the plant at design condition for this operation mode. The power production from the gas turbine as well as the auxiliary power consumption by the compressor and the oil pumps are also shown.

Figure 30: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Solar driven μ GT + Storage charging"

The following table summarizes the simulation results:

Table 15: Overview of the simulation results for "Solar driven μ GT+ Storage charging"

Air Cycle					
Compressor consumption	146.7	kW	Net electrical power output	76.9	kW _{el}
Compressor pressure ratio	3.90	-	Net thermal power output	305	kW _{th}
Solar receiver inlet temperature	190	°C	Solar receiver Heat input	498.4	kW _{th}
Turbine inlet temperature	750	°C			
Recovery heat exchanger					
Air inlet temperature	495	°C	Oil inlet temperature	126	°C
Air outlet temperature	140	°C	Oil outlet temperature	350	°C
Pressure drop (air side)	5.00	%	Pressure drop (oil side)	2.00	%
Primary oil cycle					

Oil mass flow	0.598	kg/s	Pump electrical consumption	0.163	kW
Pressure drop (down comers)	6.25	bar	Pump outlet pressure	2.616	bar
Oil Heat Exchanger					
Hot side inlet temperature	345	°C	Cold inlet temperature	100	°C
Hot side outlet temperature	130	°C	Cold outlet temperature	330	°C
Pressure drop (hot side)	3.50	%	Pressure drop (cold side)	10	%
Secondary oil cycle					
Oil mass flow	0.578	kg/s	Inlet pressure of the Storage	0.850	bar
Pump electrical consumption	0.427	kW _{el}			

4.1.1.2 Solar driven μ GT and ORC

This is another main operation scheme during daytime with high DNI and high electric power demand and/or full TES. The μ GT is driven by the solar absorber at highest possible capacity depending on the available flux on the receiver. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to ORC for maximal electrical output of plant. This operation mode will be tested in the prototype plant as one of the main targets of the project.

The state of the main components is as follows:

- Solar receiver is at operation temperature
- Compressor / receiver / μ GT are at operation air volume flow; μ GT generator is producing power
- RHEX is at operation temperature
- Primary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow
- Secondary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow to run ORC
- TES is cut off
- Valve to ORC is open & pump in ORC mixing line is controlling mass flow to keep ORC max inlet temperature

Figure 31 shows the state of the components and represents the flow direction within the plant for this operation mode.

Figure 31: Schematic diagram of operation mode “Solar driven μ GT + ORC”

Figure 32 depicts the results of the static simulation. It shows the state of the working media throughout the plant at design condition for this operation mode. The power production from the gas turbine and the ORC system as well as the auxiliary power consumption by the compressor and the oil pumps are also shown.

Figure 32: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Solar driven μGT + ORC"

Table 16 summarizes the simulation results of this operation mode. Note that only the differences compared to Table 15 are shown.

Table 16: Overview of the simulation results for "Solar driven μGT+ ORC"

Secondary oil cycle					
Oil mass flow	0.578	kg/s	ORC electrical power output	23.3	kWel
Pump electrical consumption	0.426	kWel	ORC electrical efficiency	7,92	%

4.1.1.3 Storage driven ORC

During the night or due to lack of solar irradiation, the stored energy from the TES is used to run the ORC at times when the μ GT is not running. This operation mode will be tested in the prototype plant as one of the main targets of the project.

The state of the main components is as follows:

- Air cycle is off
- Primary oil cycle is off
- HX between oil cycles is cut off from flow in secondary oil loop
- Valves in secondary oil cycle are open to enable reverse flow through TES for discharge
- TES is discharging
- Valve to ORC is open & pump in ORC mixing line is controlling mass flow to keep ORC max inlet temperature

Figure 33 shows the state of the components and represents the flow direction within the plant for this operation mode.

Figure 33: Schematic diagram of operation mode "Storage driven ORC"

Figure 34 depicts the results of the static simulation. It shows the state of the working media throughout the ORC cycle at design condition for this operation mode. The power production from the ORC system as well as the auxiliary power consumption by the oil pump is also shown. The top cycle is not operating in this operation mode.

Figure 34: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Storage driven ORC"

Table 17 summarizes the simulation results of this operation mode. Note that only the differences compared to Table 16 are shown.

Table 17: Overview of the simulation results for "Storage driven ORC"

Secondary oil cycle					
Oil mass flow	0.5	kg/s	ORC electrical power output	19.32	kWel
Pump electrical consumption	0.369	kWel	ORC electrical efficiency	7.92	%

4.1.2 Secondary Operation Modes

In this section the secondary operation modes are presented.

4.1.2.1 Fuel driven μ GT and ORC

This is another operation scheme during the time with no DNI but a high electric power demand. The μ GT is driven by the innovative combustion chamber. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally sent to ORC for maximal electrical output of plant. This operation mode will be tested in the prototype plant as one of the secondary targets of the project.

The state of the main components is as follows:

- Solar receiver is off
- Compressor / Combustor / μ GT are at operation; μ GT generator is producing el. power
- RHX is at operation temperature
- Primary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow
- Secondary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow to run ORC
- TES is cut off
- Valve to ORC is open & pump in ORC mixing line is controlling mass flow to keep ORC max inlet temperature

In this mode, the combustion chamber will provide the heat to the system instead of the solar receiver. The heat and mass balance of the plant is identical to 4.1.3.1.

4.1.2.2 Thermocline management

The effective storage capacity is reduced by the presence of the thermocline (transition zone between the cold and hot layer of the storage). At the end of every charging/discharging process this zone has to be removed; otherwise the thickness of this layer increases from cycle to cycle leading to reduced storage capacity / efficiency.

Another two different operation modes with the aim to remove the thermocline after charging and discharging processes were defined.

Thermocline management option 1

At end of charging of TES the thermocline is pushed from bottom of tank to ORC to expel the thermocline and utilize the thermal energy stored in the thermocline. This is done by opening the control valve in TES-ORC bypass line and the cold oil flow to the ORC. This operation mode will end, when the outlet temperature of TES reaches the TES inlet temperature (TES fully charged + no thermocline). This mode can only be applied as long as heat input from RHX to secondary cycle is available; otherwise cold oil would be introduced on top of the charged TES. Theoretically this operation mode could be used to run ORC after the storage is fully charged and there is still solar resource available.

It should be mentioned that the implementation of this operation mode is associated with additional instruments and technical improvements. Therefore, the possibility of implementing it will be checked again during the detailed engineering and construction phase.

Figure 33 shows the state of the components and represents the flow direction within the plant for this operation mode.

Figure 35: Schematic diagram of operation mode “Thermocline management 1”

Thermocline management option 2

At end of discharging, the thermocline is pushed to ORC to expel the thermocline and utilize the thermal energy stored in the thermocline. This is done by continuing the oil flow to ORC until the cold oil behind the thermocline reaches the ORC. This would drive the thermocline out of the storage at the end of each discharging cycle and is principally an extension of the mode “Storage driven ORC”.

Figure 36 shows the state of the components and represents the flow direction within the plant for this operation mode.

Figure 36: Schematic diagram of operation mode “Thermocline management 2”

4.1.3 Simulative Only Operation Modes

The following operation modes were determined as possible operation modes for a future system; however they are not going to be realized at the prototype within the frame of the POLYPHEM-Project.

4.1.3.1 Solar driven μ GT and ORC and Storage charging

The μ GT is driven by solar absorber. The exhaust heat is transferred to the primary oil cycle, then secondary oil cycle, and finally split and sent to ORC as well as the TES (charging) for a shifted electricity production. This operation mode is not possible with the current plant layout since the thermal power output of RHX is not sufficient to run ORC and charge TES simultaneously.

4.1.3.2 Solar and Fuel driven μ GT

In case of insufficient DNI and high demand, the air flow will be split between the solar receiver and the combustion chamber in order to reach the design air temperature after mixing the air flows. In this way, the full load operation of the gas turbine and ORC system can be guaranteed. The realization of this mode requires additional technical investigation during the detail engineering and construction phase.

4.1.3.3 Solar and Storage driven ORC

In case of insufficient DNI, energy from the storage is added to the cycle in order to maintain full load operation of ORC. This operation mode is not possible with the current plant layout since additional piping, controller etc. would be needed.

4.1.3.4 Increased Storage charging / “Max. thermal energy”

The purpose of this operation mode is to harness solar energy for storage charging when there is lower demand for electrical output of the plant. To do this, the turbine section of the μ GT is partly bypassed in order to reduce its output to a minimum to drive the compressor and thus increase the exhaust temperature of the turbine. As a result, the thermal power to charge the storage is increased.

The state of the main components is as follows:

- Solar receiver is at operation temperature
- Compressor / receiver are at operation air volume flow
- Air flow to μ GT is reduced to provide minimum thermal load
- Rest of air flow is directed through μ GT bypass (at higher temperature)
- RHX is at higher temperature (than normal solar operation)
- Primary oil cycle is operated to cool RHX and to keep oil temperature below critical temperature
- Secondary oil cycle is at operation temperature and controlled stable mass flow to charge TES
- Valve at top of TES is open and hot oil is charging TES
- ORC is off

For this mode, the RHX has to withstand higher temperatures for a rather long duration which leads to an increased material cost and the oil pumps have to deliver a higher mass flow rate. Furthermore, it will require a more complex control strategy for reducing the μ GT load and bypassing the hot air. Therefore, this operation mode cannot be covered by the prototype due to cost restrictions and is only covered by simulation.

Figure 37 depicts the results of the static simulation. It shows the state of the working media throughout the plant for this operation mode. The power production from the gas turbine as well as the auxiliary power consumption by the compressor and the oil pumps are also shown. As expected, the thermal power available from the top cycle to the bottom cycle is increased compared to the design case which lead to a faster charging of the storage. This results in a higher oil mass flow rate entering the TES which could lead to an unfavourable behaviour of the stratification.

Figure 37: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Increased Storage charging"

4.1.3.5 Electrical Storage Charging

The purpose of this mode is to use electrical surplus energy internally to heat up the thermal storage for purposes of el. net stability (compensation of electrical overloads) or temperature maintenance; or to use cheap grid energy to charge the thermal storage and provide electricity on demand (principle of "power-to-heat-to-power").

The state of the main components is as follows:

- Air cycle, primary oil cycle and secondary oil cycle are off
- Valves at TES bypass line are open to create small TES oil cycle
- Electrical Heater charges TES

For the realization of this mode, additional valves, heating elements, pump and controller are needed. The TES bypass line itself is needed anyway for pre-heating the oil cycle. In the current layout, electrical pre-heating of the oil in the secondary cycle is not necessary.

Considering the thermocline of the stratified thermal storage, electrical heating only makes sense right before or after charging with heat from RHX or for a complete charge of TES; otherwise some of the cold oil

remaining at the connecting pipes would enter through the upper part of the tank, and the stratification of the thermal storage would be negatively affected.

Figure 38 depicts the results of the static simulation. It shows the state of the working medium in the oil cycle. The power consumption by the electrical heater and the oil pump are shown. As it is seen, the oil mass flow rate is lower compared to the design condition since fast charging is not the purpose of this mode.

Figure 38: Heat and mass balance of the plant in operation mode "Electrical Storage Charging"

4.2 OVERALL PLANT LAYOUT

This chapter will briefly describe the evolution process of designing the final overall layout for the prototype. As a starting point the basic concept with its values from the project proposal was taken and iteratively expanded and concretized. An important input for this process was the definition of the main operation modes and the overall operation concept as stated in the previous chapter.

During the design process a large number of layout options of the prototype plant have been considered and solutions elaborated. The overall layout influences the specification of the sub-systems and components which in turn have an impact on the overall design. To describe this process in its entirety would extend the scope of this report. Thus, only the most important design-milestones will be explained in this chapter in detail which have a significant effect on the overall layout, whilst others are only mentioned briefly. As the top cycle provides the thermal input to the rest of the plant, the specifications of the gas turbine have the greatest influence on the overall plant layout.

As a starting point of the design process a very basic system layout was considered (see Figure 39), which is based on the conceptual layout of the project proposal.

Figure 39: Initial version of the process flow diagram

One major aspect for the design of the prototype is the height in which the solar receiver and the gas turbine will be located at. This is a special case, since the required radiative power to run the POLYPHEM set-up would result in a much smaller tower height and solar field as it is available at the THEMIS facility. In a future commercial application the tower height and the solar field size can be aligned to the desired operational parameters of the plant. In the prototype plant, however, the oil has to be pumped 80 m above ground. Not only has the oil pump to overcome this height difference, it results in a hydraulic head much higher than the thermal storage would be capable to withstand. Therefore, this set-up, internally called “one oil-cycle”, would require a pressure reducing valve and safety devices to protect components from overpressure. Moreover, it was anticipated that the control of the oil pump would be rather complex to match the cooling demand of the RHX, the pressure losses in the system and to deliver a flow rate suitable for the TES to be charged with. To tackle these issues, two possible main layout options have been examined:

1. **“Two oil-cycles”**: Separating the hydraulic circuits of the tower cycle and bottom cycle into a high pressure (tower) and low pressure system (TES, ORC)
2. **“Exhaust downstream”**: Locating the RHX on ground level and transfer the turbine exhaust through an air duct to the tower base

The first option “two oil-cycles” was analyzed in detail and discussed within the consortium. The basic design of this option is illustrated in Figure 40. The most important outcomes are summarized in Table 18 below. The investigation has shown that the “two oil-cycle” version seems to be the better choice for this project. The high pressure in the tower oil-cycle due to the geodetic height poses a safety risk for the thermal energy storage. Therefore, the two oil-cycles should be separated from each other. Another interesting advantage of this concept is that the primary oil-cycle in the tower results in a closed hydraulic circuit. Pumping up the oil to the top of the tower requires a more powerful oil pump in case of the “one oil-cycle” solution, since in this case the kinetic energy from the down coming oil has to be dissipated before entering the thermal energy storage.

Figure 40: Intermediate version of the process flow diagram introducing two separated oil cycles

Table 18: Comparison of “two oil-cycles” versus “one oil-cycle”

Advantages		Disadvantages
Two separated oil cycles (high and low pressure cycle) versus “one-cycle-solution”	+ High pressure only in primary cycle (lower risk related to secondary cycle)	- Additional pump (for circulation in tower) and heat exchanger required
	+ Control of oil mass flow becomes easier (separation of cycle to charge TES and primary cycle in tower)	- Additional temperature difference between the oil cycles -> Slightly reduced temperature in secondary cycle
	+ During start-up: Heat capacity of piping from secondary heat exchanger to TES is negligible	- Additional pump required for filling the tower piping circuit with oil (Pump operating point: High head and low flow rate)
	+ Pumps in both cycles need to be less powerful	
	+ No by-pass needed for TES during start-up	
	+ In case of an incident: Cycles can be drained separately	
	+ Less pump power needed in primary cycle (closed hydraulic circuit)	
	+ In case the existing piping in tower can be used for the primary cycle, the secondary cycle will not be in contact with possible residues in the pipe	

The second option considered was to divert the exhaust gas downwards the tower and to install the recovery heat exchanger at ground level of the tower. This option would leave the tower facility completely free of oil, which is clearly a benefit in terms of safety and security. However, there are clear reasons against this option. The main argument against this option is that it is less in line with the design of a potential commercial POLYPHEM-like plant. Especially the interaction between the gas turbine and the recovery heat exchanger cannot be tested under realistic conditions in this configuration. An additional air blower would be necessary to compensate the pressure losses in the air duct. Not only is this measure expensive, it would also distort a realistic interaction between the components. Therefore, it was decided to no longer pursue this option. A comparison between the options “exhaust downstream” and “two oil-cycle” can be found in Table 19:

Table 19: Comparison of “exhaust downstream” versus “two oil-cycles”

Advantages		Disadvantages
Exhaust downstream versus two-cycles	+ No oil in top of tower	- Less realistic operation conditions of recovery heat exchanger in terms of commercialization of concept (RHX not located close to μ GT)
	+ No expansion tank in tower needed	- To compensate thermal losses in the air d thick insulation

	+ Only one oil pump for bottom cycle needed	- Additional expensive air blower needed to compensate pressure losses
	+ No oil/oil heat exchanger required	- Existing piping in tower cannot be used for oil cycle
		- New air ducts of at least 300 mm required from tower top to bottom

Besides these two main considerations concerning the overall plant layout stated above another option in order to enhance the overall plant efficiency was being addressed. This option was to enhance the cycle efficiency of the ORC by implementing an economizer. An additional heat exchanger would be implemented in the exhaust stream of the gas turbine behind the RHX to heat up water. This could be used for preheating purposes of the ORC, which needs approx. one third of the heat input only for preheating the working fluid before evaporation. This would result in a lower heat demand of the ORC at times when the gas turbine is in operation and a larger share of thermal energy could be transferred to the storage. An analysis of this option was carried out and the main results are summarized in Table 20. Due to the excessive effort to implement this - in fact quite reasonable option- in the context of this project, this option was not considered any further.

Table 20: Consideration of economizer for the ORC

	Advantages	Disadvantages
Economizer for preheating of ORC (HX after RHX)	+ More efficient ORC-Cycle	- Additional heat exchanger required
		- Additional piping required
		- Heat exchanger would create additional pressure loss and decreases the efficiency of the gas turbine
		- System works only during times the gas turbine is running

Further details worth mentioning with regard to the overall design will be described briefly hereinafter. These features, among other things, result also from a hazard and operability study (HAZOP). This study had focused on the gas cycle (micro gas turbine) and the primary/secondary oil cycle. Operation issues and risks based on the current design have been identified within this study and risk mitigations measures determined. While a major part of these identified mitigation measures can be implemented within the instrumentation and control system of the plant, which is being developed in another task of this project, several of the measures have an influence on the overall layout / process flow scheme of the prototype. At this point it should be mentioned that some aspects examined go beyond the scope of the overall plant layout and merge with the general engineering (e.g. valve types and positions, instrumentation), since a strict separation of these tasks would not have been expedient.

The outcomes of the overall layout have been incorporated in Figure 41: Final Version of the process flow diagram including instrumentation (at the editorial deadline of this report).

Waste-Gate-System

The so called “Waste-Gate-System” is a kind of a bypass around the solar receiver and the gas turbine. The compressor discharge gas will be drawn-off to the RHX without passing the turbine. This feature works in the event of a turbine overspeed, caused by a spontaneous electrical load collapse, and will ensure that the turbine is not being damaged. A modification of this feature could also be used for the described operation mode *Increased Storage charging / “Max. thermal energy”*, however, implementing this detail places higher demands on the RHX in terms of long-term thermal stress.

RHX By-Pass

In case the oil temperature or the oil mass flow is not sufficient to provide enough cooling capacity for the RHX while the gas turbine is running, the exhaust air is redirected around the RHX to protect it from overheating.

TES By-Pass

During start-up of the plant the TES will be by-passed in order to not affect the stratification by introducing oil with an inappropriate temperature. This by-pass-line can also be equipped with a flow heater to protect the oil from undercooling when the plant is not operated for a longer period of time and the ambient temperature is low. If Jarytherm DBT becomes too cold, its kinematic viscosity (e.g. 259 mm²/s at 0 °C) prevents pumping. In case the operation mode *Electrical Storage Charging* will be implemented this heating device could be adapted to those needs.

Expansion Tanks

The primary and secondary oil cycles require expansion vessels at suitable locations to compensate the expansion of the oil (density varies around 200 kg/m³ from 30 – 300 °C).

Recirculation Line of ORC

The ORC-module operates in a specific operating temperature range which is lower than the set point temperature of the oil after the RHX and within the storage. Therefore, a recirculation line is needed to achieve a mixing temperature to feed the ORC.

Nitrogen Overpressure

Jarytherm DBT requires an atmosphere without oxygen. Therefore, the vessels will be pressurized with approximately 150 mbar Nitrogen overpressure in order to avoid the air entrance to the tank and compensate the thermal expansion during charge and discharge processes.

Load Bank

In order to allow testing of the components in an off-grid setting, frequency converters and a load bank will be implemented to take up the electrical load of the gas turbine generator and the ORC-module.

Draining Valves

In order allow oil drainage, for each one-way valve there should be a draining valve.

Oil Collecting Basin

In case of a leakage in any oil-bearing body collecting basins have to be implemented to prevent the oil from penetrating the ground.

Figure 41: Final Version of the process flow diagram including instrumentation (at the editorial deadline of this report)

5. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Within this task the demonstration plant was designed fundamentally. The main outcome of the design process is the characteristic of the main components. The main design parameters of the plant are summarized in Table 21. Additionally, the operating range of the prototype plant has been evaluated and determined. The layout determined to be the most suitable for the prototype plant couples the top and the bottom cycle with two separated oil-cycles. This basic layout will serve as base for the detailed design process which will be supplemented by an external engineering company. A profound simulation model for the system is under development in WP7. Eventually the complete system will be assembled ‘on-site’ and thoroughly tested under solar conditions, providing the opportunity to confirm the overall technical concept as well as to validate various simulation models.

Table 21: Summary of System Specifications from POLYPHEM Proposal

Top Cycle (Air cycle)	Proposal	Final Design	Unit
Ambient pressure	850	830	mbar
Ambient temperature	20	15	°C
Air mass flowrate	0.6	0.82	kg/s
Compressor discharge pressure	2.98	3.32	bar
Compressor discharge temperature	140	190	°C
Solar receiver name plate capacity (input)	380	≈ 600	kW _{th}
Solar receiver available heat (output)	305	≈ 500	kW _{th}
Turbine Inlet temperature	750	750	°C
Maximum pressure drop in the solar receiver	< 5 %	170 mbar	-
Turbine outlet temperature	550	495	°C
Turbine outlet pressure	895	840	mbar
Recovery heat exchanger outlet temperature	120	140	°C
Maximum pressure drop in the RHEX	< 5 %	10 mbar	-
RHEX capacity	215	≈ 340	kW _{th}
μGT electrical power output	40	76.5	kW _{el}
Oil cycle & Thermal Energy Storage (TES)			
Inlet temperature of the TES	330	330	°C
Outlet temperature of the TES	100	100	°C
TES capacity	2	2.6	MWh _{th}
Heat Transfer Fluid	-	Jarytherm® DBT	-
Design oil mass flow	-	0.7	kg/s
ORC cycle			
Turbine inlet temperature	150	150	°C
Electrical power output	20	25	kW _{el}

